

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN USING DIGITAL EXTENSIVE READING TOOLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article analyzes international experience in using digital extensive reading tools in foreign language education. The integration of digital technologies into the learning process helps increase students' motivation to read, develop independent learning skills, and improve overall language competence. The study highlights the role of digital platforms and resources in developing reading skills, vocabulary, and critical thinking. The findings indicate that digital extensive reading tools can significantly enhance the effectiveness of foreign language learning.

Key words: extensive reading, digital platforms, foreign experience.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy til ta'limida raqamli ekstensiv o'qish vositalaridan foydalanish bo'yicha xalqaro tajriba tahlil qilinadi. Raqamli texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish o'quvchilarning o'qishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirish, mustaqil ta'lim ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda til kompetensiyasini takomillashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqotda raqamli platformalar va resurslarning o'qish ko'nikmalari, so'z boyligi va tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi. Natijalar raqamli ekstensiv o'qish vositalari xorijiy til o'rganish samaradorligini oshirishda muhim omil ekanini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekstensiv o'qish, raqamli platformalar, xorijiy tajriba.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется международный опыт использования цифровых инструментов экстенсивного чтения в обучении иностранным языкам. Интеграция цифровых технологий в образовательный процесс способствует повышению мотивации студентов к чтению, развитию навыков самостоятельного обучения и совершенствованию языковой компетенции. В статье также рассматривается роль цифровых платформ и ресурсов в развитии навыков чтения, расширении словарного запаса и формировании критического мышления. Результаты исследования показывают, что использование цифровых инструментов экстенсивного чтения повышает эффективность изучения иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: экстенсивное чтение, цифровые платформы, зарубежный опыт.

Extensive reading (ER) is considered one of the most effective approaches to developing language proficiency in foreign language learning. It encourages learners to

read large amounts of meaningful and comprehensible texts, which contributes to the improvement of reading fluency, vocabulary development, and overall language competence. In recent years, the integration of digital technologies into education has created new opportunities for implementing extensive reading through online platforms and digital resources. These tools provide learners with easy access to diverse reading materials and allow teachers to monitor students' reading progress more effectively. Therefore, exploring international experience in the use of digital extensive reading tools has become increasingly important for improving the quality of foreign language education.

Julian Bamford and Richard R. Day are main figures in spreading the use of extensive reading in EFL context. They describe extensive reading as a learning approach in which students read a substantial amount of relatively easy texts in the target language in order to develop language proficiency [1]. Similarly, William Grabe and Fredricka L. Stoller note that extensive reading allows learners to engage with large volumes of texts that are within their linguistic ability while also being enjoyable and meaningful [2]. Similar to scholars stated above, Richard Davis emphasizes that extensive reading programs should provide learners with sufficient time, appropriate materials, and encouragement to read independently and for pleasure at their own level, without the pressure of formal assessment [3]

In spite of the above mentioned benefits of ER, some researchers argue that implementing ER programmes has some problems including lack of reading materials, insufficient preparations of teachers, the teacher-centred views of learning, and lack of time for teachers as they face a great deal of pressure to complete the syllabus. Some studies indicate that teachers have certain concerns regarding the implementation of extensive reading. According to D. Brown, one of these issues is the difficulty of determining whether students have actually read the assigned materials, while another challenge is the limited classroom time available to organize extensive reading activities [4]. K. McBride and B. Milliner note that digital tools such as MReader can help address these problems by allowing teachers to monitor students' reading progress more effectively and manage extensive reading programs more efficiently. MReader allows teachers to monitor students' reading progress through short comprehension quizzes based on graded readers. Another popular platform is Xreading, which provides learners with access to a large digital library of graded reading materials from different publishers and enables teachers to track students' reading performance. Similarly, Oxford Reading Club offers a collection of digital graded readers together with interactive activities that support the development of reading comprehension and vocabulary. In addition, ER-Central provides free online resources for extensive reading, including reading materials and assessment tools designed to encourage regular reading practice. Another platform, Raz-Kids, offers leveled digital books with audio support and comprehension tasks, making it particularly useful for developing learners' reading skills. These digital tools create flexible learning environments and give learners easy access to a wide range of reading materials, supporting the development of reading fluency, vocabulary growth, and overall language proficiency.

Despite their advantages, digital extensive reading platforms also have certain limitations. One of the main challenges is their dependence on stable internet access and digital devices, which may not always be available in all educational organizations. In addition, some platforms require paid subscriptions, which can limit access for certain

institutions or learners. Another concern is that teachers may find it difficult to ensure that students have actually read the assigned materials, as learners might complete quizzes without fully engaging with the texts. Furthermore, effective use of these tools requires both teachers and students to possess adequate digital literacy skills.

In conclusion, digital extensive reading tools play an important role in supporting foreign language learning by providing learners with easy access to diverse reading materials and flexible learning environments. They help improve reading fluency, vocabulary development, and overall language competence. Despite certain limitations, the effective integration of these tools can significantly enhance the implementation of extensive reading programs in modern language education.

References:

1. Bamford, J., & Day, R. R. (2003). *Extensive reading activities for teaching language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. L. (2002). *Teaching and researching reading*. London: Pearson Education.
3. Davis, R. (1995). Extensive reading: An expensive extravagance? *ELT Journal*, 49(4), 329-336.
4. Brown, D. (2012). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy* (4th ed.). New York: Pearson Education.
5. McBride, K., & Milliner, B. (2018). The use of M-Reader to promote extensive reading in EFL contexts. *Journal of Extensive Reading*, 6(1), 1-15.